

Exploring possibilities to fortify hydroponically grown baby vegetables with Fe and Zn

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Micronutrient malnutrition, primarily the result of diets poor in bio-available vitamins and minerals, affects more than half of the world's population. Two micronutrients that are widely recognized by the World Health Organization (WHO) as limiting are iron and zinc.

In order to screen 5 botanically distinct vegetable species with respect to their reactions to increased supply of Fe and Zn, an experiment was set up under semi-controlled conditions. Seeds were sown in the mixture of agroperlite (AGROPERLIT EXTRA, Termika Zrenjanin) and sand. About 100 seeds of chard, onion, red beet, kohlrabi or lettuce were sown and grown hydroponically using Hoagland nutrient solution (HS, control). After emergence, three treatments were introduced: HS with doubled concentration of Fe, HS with doubled concentration of Zn and HS with doubled concentrations of Fe and Zn. Experiment was set in three replications and treatment lasted up to 30 days. Aerial plant parts were harvested and analyzed for Fe, Zn, ash, photosynthetic pigments and vitamin C content.

In lettuce, concentration of photosynthetic pigments and vitamin C increased in the presence of added Fe and Zn whereas concentration of Fe declined. In chard, concentration of photosynthetic pigments also increased, but to a smaller extent as compared to the lettuce. Concentration of Zn increased in chard to which it was added. In red beet, concentration of Fe increased over 75% but yield concomitantly decreased 35% upon addition of Fe. In onion, concentration of vitamin C and photosynthetic pigments increased in all treatments with respect to control, whereas percentage of ash, Zn and Fe declined. In kohlrabi yield increased in the presence of additional Fe. Concentration of chlorophylls significantly increased whereas concentration of carotenoids declined.

Concentration of both Fe and Zn increased only in red beets and of Zn in chard. All three treatments increased biomass production only in kohlrabi.